

Project Title	Global cooperation on FAIR data policy and practice
Project Acronym	WorldFAIR
Grant Agreement No	101058393
Instrument	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01
Topic, type of action	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-41 HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions
Start Date of Project	2022-06-01
Duration of Project	24 months
Project Website	http://worldfair-project.eu

M12: Urban Health Data - Learning and training workshop: How to create a data management plan with CARE and FAIR: introduction to essential concepts and best practices in data management and sharing for researchers and practitioners in urban/ public health

Work Package	WP08 Urban Health
Lead Author (Org)	Ana Ortigoza (Urban Health Collaborative - Drexel University)
Contributing Author(s) (Org)	Ran Li (Urban Health Collaborative - Drexel University) Usama Bilal (Drexel University) Theresa Anderson (CODATA consultant)
Due Date	24.11.2023
Date	30.11.2023
Version	1.0 DRAFT NOT YET APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10231435

Dissemination Level

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU: Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)

Introduction

The purpose of WorldFAIR WP08 is to advance the FAIR and CARE principles [Wilkinson 2016; Russo Carroll 2021] in the practices of Urban Health research. To do this, the WP is developing guidelines and training in best practice. Interim guidelines were developed and presented in

D8.1 “Urban Health Data - Guidelines and Recommendations”.¹ These guidelines and other work then informed the development of training materials for the course “How to create a data management plan with CARE and FAIR: introduction to essential concepts and good practices in data management and sharing for researchers and practitioners in urban/ public health” which was delivered as a special component of the Summer Course series at the Urban Health Collaborative - Drexel University during the week of 26-30 June 2023.

The present Milestone (WorldFAIR MS 12) provides information about the course for which the training materials were developed. The materials used in the workshop are available at <https://zenodo.org/records/10231138>. The materials will be further developed and refined through a consultation workshop and presented in D8.2 as the final version of the training materials and the documentation guidelines.

Course description and relevance

Urban health requires the interconnection of knowledge and practices from different disciplines to depict the complexity of urban systems. This poses several challenges in the study of urban health such as the need for a common vocabulary (i.e., how we define urban areas, informal settlements); the use of data from different sources (i.e., place based and spatial data, health registries); the creation of data that could be comparable across urban areas and over time (i.e. accounting for differences between cities and within cities over time), among others [Quistberg 2019]. All these challenges are closely related to the principles of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and CARE (Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility, and

¹ Ortigoza, A., Moore, K., Quitsberg, A., Li, R., Lazo-Elizondo, M., & Diez Roux, A. (2023). WorldFAIR Project (D8.1) Urban Health Data - Guidelines and Recommendations (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7887523>

DRAFT NOT YET APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Ethics) data policies and practices [Wilkinson 2016; Russo Carroll 2021]. The implementation of these principles contributes to a more transparent, efficient, participatory, technology enabled, and interdisciplinary science to tackle current and future global societal challenges.

Beginning in 2023, all NIH-funded grant applications or renewals that generate scientific data must include a robust and detailed plan for how researchers will manage and share data during the entire funded period (data management and sharing plan, DMSP) [NIH Data Management and Sharing Policy 2023]. This includes information on data storage, access policies/procedures, preservation, metadata standards, and distribution approaches, which are closely related to the knowledge and implementation of FAIR and CARE principles.

The common understanding of the FAIR and CARE principles is fragmented and uneven among researchers and practitioners in urban health. Therefore, the overall purpose of this course is to provide participants with a broad understanding of FAIR and CARE principles that could help them to design and develop data management plans for research and community -based projects according to NIH data management requirements.

Course objectives

1. Understand concepts and frameworks related to FAIR and CARE principles in Open Science
2. Recognize and compare challenges in FAIR and CARE implementation within the Urban Health discipline.
3. Identify components and requirements of a data management plan development

4

'Global cooperation on FAIR data policy and practice' (WorldFAIR) has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe project call HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-01, grant agreement 101058393.

DRAFT NOT YET APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

4. Develop critical acumen with respect to the assessment of strength and weakness of data management plans and the impacts and benefits of FAIR and CARE data principles implementation

Target audience

Target audience was intended to reach people from many disciplines including public health, health care, data science, as well as public health practitioners working with data in community projects. No prerequisites were required.

Instruction method

The course was taught during the Summer Course series at the Urban Health Collaborative-Drexel University during the week of 26-30 June 2023, for a total of 15 hours in the week.

Modality included for each day, the delivery of remote asynchronous pre-recorded self-paced lectures (~ 1.5 hours) and then a remote synchronous (or in-person)² discussion/ practical sessions (~ 1.5 hours). From day 2 on, there was practical time each day in which participants integrated concepts and practice, building towards the completion and discussion of the data management plans that were presented at the end of the course (day 5). Course schedule and content is available in Appendix 1.

A pre- and post- course survey was conducted to understand the level of knowledge

² Although the course was thought to be hybrid (remote and in-person) at this instance no student opted for the in-person option.

DRAFT NOT YET APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

participants had about FAIR and CARE principles in advance of the course and how that would have changed after attending it. Pre- and post-course survey models are available in Appendix 1.

Course results

A total of 10 participants attended the course. One participant was involved in academic research and the rest of the group were from the Philadelphia Health Department. Most of them referred to frequently working in data collection and processing of secondary sources, using data for monitoring and research, or having responsibility for stewarding data (Figure 1).

Results from the pre- course survey showed that there was very low to low knowledge of FAIR and CARE principles as well as in metadata schemas and preservation policies, in advance to the course. (Figure 2). After the course, the overall perception of participants acquired more understanding of these concepts (Figure 3).

Figure 1. Frequency and /or likelihood of performing data- related tasks at work.

Footnote: Axis X shows the number of participants (total = 10 respondents); Axis Y shows the frequency or likelihood of performing the tasks described with colored bars.

Figure 2. Level of knowledge, experience, and/or familiarity with FAIR and CARE – related concepts before the course

Footnote: Axis X shows the number of participants (total = 10 respondents); Axis Y shows the level of knowledge/ expertise/ familiarity of participants with concepts described with colored bars.

Figure 3. Level of knowledge, experience, and/or familiarity with FAIR and CARE – related concepts after the course

Footnote: Axis X shows the number of participants (total = 10 respondents); Axis Y shows the level of knowledge/ expertise/ familiarity (1 =very low; 2 = low; 3 = moderate; 4 = high; 5 = very high) of participants with concepts described with colored bars.

Some conclusions and next steps in the elaboration of training materials

- Regarding the audience, we were expecting more researchers and academic faculty members using primary or secondary data for quantitative research to attend the course. We suspect this low attendance may be because of the mistaken belief that these topics are not key or central in their work but mostly matter to data managers / data scientists. There is a need to better inform urban health researchers or these requirements and the benefits for their work. The final iteration of the training materials will also include advocacy materials drawing attention to e.g. the NIH requirements and the benefits of the FAIR and CARE principles. Moreover, as these requirements become more commonplace, we believe training of this nature will be more well attended.
- One of the difficulties / challenges seen during the course was the exemplification of FAIR and CARE principles or whether participants could find ways of operationalizing these principles in their everyday work and in each instance of the data cycle. More work will be done to better identify such examples and this will be one of the topics of the consultation workshop.
- Further activities planned for future editions of the training module will involve seminars and discussion sessions where faculties and researchers from different centers/ schools at Drexel University can be involved (such as the Ubuntu Center for Race and Ethnicity Research on Health Inequities, Urban Health Collaborative, Drexel I-School and the Metadata Center).

DRAFT NOT YET APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

- As noted in the introduction, the materials will be further developed and refined through a consultation workshop and presented in WorldFAIR D8.2 as the final version of the training materials and the documentation guidelines.

DRAFT NOT YET APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

References

NIH Data Management and Sharing Policy 2023 [Last date accessed 1/13/2023]
<https://grants.nih.gov/grants/guide/notice-files/NOT-OD-21-013.html>

Quistberg D , Diez Roux A et al. (2019) Building a Data Platform for Cross-Country Urban Health Studies: the SALURBAL Study. J Urban Health 2019- 96:311–337.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11524-018-00326-0>

Russo Carroll S et al. (2021) Operationalizing the CARE and FAIR Principles for Indigenous data futures. Nature -Scientific Data. 2021 8:108. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-021-00892-0>

Wilkinson M et al. (2016) The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Nature- Scientific Data. 2016 -3:160018 <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

Appendix 1.

Course schedule

Day 1	
Asynchronous - before sync session	Introduction to FAIR principles
	Be FAIR and CARE
	NIH and other organizations requirements for Data Management Plans
	Presentation of SALURBAL and WorldFAIR projects
Sync 1.1: Intro and async recap (2:30 - 3.00 pm)	Introductions (20 minutes) Minute paper (5 minutes)
Sync 1.2: Practical FAIR - Big Picture template DMS (3:00 - 4:00 pm)	Practical: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DMS Key concepts - Things not strings: Orchid - Controlled vocabulary - Shared Ontology - Collect FAIR metadata with CEDAR - CEDAR to repository

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Utilize industry tools to integrated metadata and data <p>Discussion:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Discuss with students to see what deliverable they would like to build on day 5 - Urban Health Ontology
Day 2	
Asynchronous - before sync session	FAIR case study 1: SALURBAL FAIR implementation profile
	FAIR case study 2: SALURBALsurvey harmonization
	FAIR case study 3: SALURBAL race/ ethnicity screening of data in health information sources
Sync 2.1: Async recap (1:00 - 1:15 pm)	Comments and discussion on day 1
Sync 2.2 Exercise: craft and deploy a urban health specific ontology (1:15 - 2:15pm)	<p>Tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sheets2rdf - OntoStack
Asynchronous- End-day Activity (2.15 - 2.30 pm)	Share your own case study/ experience (if you have it) in the discussion board

Day 3	
Asynchronous - before sync session	Introduction to CARE principles
	Indigenous Data Sovereignty: Origins of CARE principles
	CARE case study: SALURBAL data handling of live births
	Challenges around CARE
Sync 3.1: Async recap (1:00 - 1:15 pm)	Comments and discussion on day 2
Sync 3.2 Exercise: Collect FAIR metadata with CEDAR workbench (1:15 - 2:15 pm)	Tools: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CEDAR Workbench - Deposit FAIR Metadata from CEDAR into a repository
Asynchronous- End-day Activity (2.15 - 2.30 pm)	Share your own challenges with CARE in the discussion board
Day 4	
Asynchronous - before sync	6 key principles for building trust in data and community

session	Building Trust in data in Urban and Public Health
	Data sovereignty and legitimacy: a New Zealand example
Sync 4.1: Async recap (1:00 - 1:15 pm)	Comments and discussion on day 3
Sync 4.2 Exercise: Industry solutions (1:15 - 2:30 pm)	Transition to Industry Solutions Tools: - Github - DBT
Day 5	
Asynchronous - before sync session	Integration of FAIR and CARE with your context. Limitations of real context
	FAIR and CARE on the 'edges': - Data in contexts of crisis/ emergency - Other challenges
	Comments and discussion on day 4.

<p>Sync 5.1 Exercise: Wrapping it up DMP (1:00 - 2:00 pm)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wrap up remainidg tasks - Deploy to ICPSR <p>Deliverable:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - template DMS - hands on experience with ORCID
<p>Sync 5.2: Async recap (2:00 - 2:30 pm)</p>	<p>Conclusions- Course perception/ feedback</p>
<p>Asynchronous- End-day Activity</p>	<p>Post- course survey</p>

Pre- course Survey

Dear participants:

Thank you for your interest in the course *“How to create a data management plan with CARE and FAIR: introduction to essential concepts and good practices in data management and sharing for researchers and practitioners in urban/ public health”*.

Before starting the course, we would like to know more about the expectations that participants have for this course. This brief, anonymous survey, which will not take more than 15 minutes to complete, will help us to accommodate the contents of the course to your needs.

For us it would be very useful if the majority of the participants could complete this survey. If you decide to answer it, once you finish, we would appreciate it if you could encourage other participants to complete it as well.

We hope this course will be a lot of shared learning!

See you soon,

Ran, Ana, and Theresa

DRAFT NOT YET APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Tell us a bit about you...

1. What is your role and your organization (affiliation and position)?

0. Would you be able to attend synchronous activities in person or remotely?
 - o In person
 - o Remotely
 - o Either way

0. What motivated you to enroll in this course?

0. What would you like to have accomplished by the end of this course?

Now a bit about data and work...

1. On a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 is very infrequent or unlikely and 5 is very likely and frequent, please tell us about your everyday work

	1	2	3	4	5
I work in the creation of instruments and guidelines for primary data collection					
I collect, process, and consolidate data from secondary sources					

I train personnel in the release of surveys and questionnaires					
I work in the community collecting data					
I use data for monitoring and research					
I have responsibility for stewarding data <u>within</u> my organisation					
I have responsibility for stewarding data <u>by liaising with</u> the communities from whom the data is collected					

0. On a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 is the lowest level of knowledge and experience and 5 is the highest level, please indicate the level of knowledge and familiarity you have regarding the following ideas.

	1	2	3	4	5
FAIR principles					
CARE principles					
Metadata schemas					
Metadata preservation policies					
Identifier services					

DRAFT NOT YET APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

0. Can you give an example of your everyday work when you face challenges with using/handling data?

0. Is there anything else you would like us to know?

Post- course Survey

Dear participants:

Thank you for your participation in the course “*How to create a data management plan with CARE and FAIR: introduction to essential concepts and good practices in data management and sharing for researchers and practitioners in urban/ public health*”.

For us it was a pleasure sharing time and experiences with you over this week, and we look forward to keeping connected with you through different channels.

We kindly ask you if you could complete this post- course survey. It would help us to improve and refine the content of this course for future iterations.

We hope this course has been helpful to you!
See you soon,

Ran, Ana, and Theresa

After these 5 days of intensive learning about FAIR and CARE principles...

1. Were you able to accomplish what motivated you to enroll in this course? Tell us how and why .

0. On a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 is the lowest level of knowledge and experience and 5 is the highest level, please indicate the level of knowledge and familiarity you have regarding the following ideas

	1	2	3	4	5
FAIR principles					
CARE principles					
Metadata schemas					
Metadata preservation policies					
Identifier services					

0. Is there anything else you would like us to know?